

A Modular COTS-based High-Efficient Sub-THz Channel Sounder and Experimental Validations

Peize Zhang*, Cihan Barış Fındık*, Pekka Kyösti*[†], Veikko Hovinen*, Klaus Nevala*, Nuutti Tervo*, Marko E. Leinonen*, Aarno Pärssinen*

*Centre for Wireless Communications, University of Oulu, 90570 Oulu, Finland

[†]Keysight Technologies Finland Oy, 90590 Oulu, Finland
peize.zhang@oulu.fi, pekka.kyosti@oulu.fi

Abstract—The prospect of offering huge amounts of available bandwidth to achieve extremely high data rates makes sub-terahertz (sub-THz) communication seen as a key enabler for 6G use cases requiring extreme throughputs on the order of 10s or 100s of Gbps. The design and planning of wireless communication systems are affected by the radio channels in which they will operate. Physical modeling of sub-THz channels requires sufficient channel-sounding data collected across multiple frequency bands and environments for statistical analysis. In this paper, we present a modular correlation-based sub-THz channel sounder using commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) instruments. It can be easily scaled for multi-band channel measurements by using different frequency extenders while sharing the same baseband units. The validation measurements at 150 GHz are conducted in an indoor corridor using the proposed sounder, together with the ray-tracing simulation results for performance validations in identical settings.

Index Terms—Channel measurements, modular design, radio propagation, sub-THz channel sounder

I. INTRODUCTION

Sub-terahertz (sub-THz) band (100–300 GHz) communication is expected to satisfy ever-increasing wireless traffic demands in 6G and beyond systems since large swathes of bandwidth are available for land-mobile and fixed service applications [1]–[3]. However, sub-THz systems suffer from higher path loss compared with the systems operating in sub-6 GHz and millimeter-wave bands, which makes it challenging to realize the desired coverage. Meanwhile, their wavelengths become comparable to the physical sizes of most environmental objects and some cases the surface roughness, thereby causing significant frequency selectivity and scattering effect. For example, experimental results have shown that less number of non-line-of-sight (NLOS) paths can be detected in sub-THz channels [4]–[6], which experience substantial attenuation in comparison with the dominant path, e.g., line-of-sight (LOS) path, if it exists. Overall, a thorough understanding of radio propagation is essential for sub-THz device and system design and performance evaluation.

Physical analysis of radio channel characteristics is based on extensive channel measurement campaigns across different frequencies and scenarios. Only then can statistical channel models be derived, whereas most existing models are only valid up to 100 GHz due to a lack of sufficient sub-THz channel measurement data. With the development of sub-THz radio frequency (RF) components, e.g., up- and down-

converters, several channel sounders have been recently proposed as reported in [5]–[10].

There are two commonly used channel sounding methods, i.e., vector network analyzer (VNA)-based frequency-domain method and time-domain method. The main challenge of sub-THz VNA-based channel sounders is the limited support for long-range measurements with sufficient dynamic range due to long RF cables and their phase stability. The radio-over-fiber technique could reduce the transmission loss in the cables and further extend the measurable transmitter-receiver (Tx-Rx) separation distance, which has been employed in sub-THz channel sounding [6], [11]. However, the phase variation introduced by the optical fiber cables becomes more significant in sub-THz bands. In [10], a VNA-based phase-compensated channel sounder was developed for 220–300 GHz phase-coherent measurements. However, VNA-based channel sounders adopt the stepped frequency-sweeping method, which is time-consuming if using a larger number of frequency points in the sweep and lower intermediate frequencies (IF) bandwidth. Time-domain sub-THz channel sounder is based on the direct sequence spread spectrum (DSSS) technique [5], [7]–[9], which yields channel impulse response (CIR) without the implementation of inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) operation. Such a system transmits a known sounding sequence, whose auto-correlation function can be approximated by a Dirac-impulse-shaped function. At the Rx side, the received signal is correlated with the identical stimulus signal, where cross-correlation can be completed via sliding correlator (SC) [5], [9] or pre-processing on a computer [7], [8]. The SC-based sounder consist of separated RF components operating in specific frequency bands, which reduces its flexibility to support multi-band channel measurements. In [7], 300 GHz correlation-based sounder has been developed, where base unit provides power and clock signal for customer-designed ultra wide-band (UWB) modules and frequency extenders. Due to the modular design, the sounder could be easily extended to perform 4×4 MIMO channel measurements [12]. Considering modularity offers benefits, e.g., flexibility in system design and upgrade, commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) measuring instruments are utilized for 300 GHz channel sounder development as presented in [8]. Here, Tx and Rx signals operate at different IFs due to using asymmetric up- and down-converters. Moreover, in-phase (I)

and quadrature (Q) IF signals are respectively fed into the sub-THz I/Q Tx module and mix with the same local oscillator (LO) signals before combining I/Q signals at RF.

In terms of correlation-based sub-THz channel sounder design, a vital issue is to improve its flexibility so that the sounder can support multi-band sub-THz channel measurements by sharing the same baseband unit and only replacing few RF components, e.g., frequency extenders, waveguide filters, and power amplifiers. In this paper, a modular sub-THz channel sounder based on COTS equipment is developed which can support measurement up to 300 GHz. The performance of the proposed sounder is evaluated via 150 GHz over-the-air (OTA) measurements in an indoor environment. Moreover, we compare with the ray-tracing simulation results using the same setup.

II. CHANNEL SOUNDER DESIGN

A. Hardware Architecture

The schematic block diagram of the proposed sub-THz channel sounder is shown in Fig. 1, which enables to measure the CIR in the time domain directly with a high dynamic range. In order to achieve higher processing gain, the channel sounder transmits a Golay complementary sequence pair [13] with a length of L instead of widely used pseudorandom noise (PN) sequence [5], [12]. The sounding sequence is generated on the personal computer (PC) and after a two-stage process of zero-insertion by a factor of 2 and digital pulse shaping with root-raised-cosine (RRC) filter, stored transmitted waveform is downloaded to the Keysight M8195A arbitrary waveform generator (AWG). Note that both real and imaginary parts of the given column of waveform data are loaded into channel 1 of the AWG. The modulated IF signal is first filtered by a bandpass filter (BPF), and then in the Virginia Diodes Inc. (VDI) spectrum analyzer extension (SAX) module (working in the block up-conversion mode), it is mixed with the LO signal supplied by Keysight E8257C PSG analog signal generator (ASG). Here, we can use different frequency extenders to perform the channel sounder for the measurements across various frequency bands. The filtered RF signal is amplified by a power amplifier (PA) before being radiated by a Tx antenna.

At the Rx side, an identical VDI SAX module (working in the block down-conversion mode) downconverts the received RF signal to an IF by mixing with the LO signal from AnaPico APMS40G-2 multi-channel signal generator. The IF signal is captured and digitized by Keysight UXR0404AP Infiniium UXR real-time oscilloscope. Measurement on directly sampled signals can be made if a high-performance oscilloscope is employed to support higher real-time bandwidth. However, through a process of digital down-conversion, it is possible to improve the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), corresponding to the increase in dynamic range. Specifically, we are *tuning* to the center frequency of the oscilloscope input signal and *resampling* the signal at a lower rate, i.e., within the bandwidth of interest. This process can be completed in Keysight PathWave vector signal analysis (VSA) 89600 software, which not only provides higher processing gain but also reduces the size of the

data set. The resulting digitally down-converted (or baseband) samples are then transferred to a PC for further processing. Following the same approach, before the decimation by a factor of 2, the stored received signal is filtered by an identical RRC filter on the PC in order to minimize intersymbol interference. Pre- and post-processing are also performed on the PC, including cross-correlation operation and channel parameter estimation.

The main instruments, i.e., AWG, oscilloscope, and ASG, share the same 10 MHz external reference clock signals from AnaPico signal generator. Furthermore, the 10 MHz reference signals could be provided via two independent Rubidium atomic clocks for synchronization rather than a wired connection between Tx and the Rx [8]. The oscilloscope will capture and save the input signal once received the external triggering pulse signal from the Keysight 33600A waveform generator. The period of the trigger signal is the same as the sounding stimulus signal period, which enables time alignment between transmitter and receiver for absolute propagation delay measurement [14].

B. Antenna Subsystem and Specifications

The appropriate choice of the sounding waveform determines the time-domain channel parameters that can be estimated, as well as the accuracy and resolution that can be achieved. Besides, depending on the spatial channel parameters of interest, a number of antennas can be employed in the channel sounders. It is highly demanded to focus the sub-THz signal into a desired beam direction for data transmission due to high path loss. Exploring sub-THz double-directional channel characteristics becomes more important for channel measurements and modeling. Since there are no commercial sub-THz phased arrays or high-gain omnidirectional antennas, the directional scanning sounding (DSS) with high-gain directional antennas is the most popular way to collect directional CIRs [5], [6], [9]. Such a method can be easily implemented with an antenna rotator, where sub-THz standard gain horn antenna is mechanically aligned to a desired direction, but at the expense of longer measurement duration if a full three-dimensional (3D) scanning is conducted.

There are two ways to perform DSS method, where 1) horn antenna rotates to desired directions *step-by-step* and remains motionless in each direction while the oscilloscope makes a single acquisition of a specific number of samples or data points (known as record length), or 2) horn antenna *continuously* rotates in 2π azimuth plane and the oscilloscope repeatedly collects data triggered by external pulse signals. Compared with the step-by-step rotation mode, the continuous rotation mode could shorten the measurement time introduced by the mechanical rotation of the directional antenna, i.e., the time for acceleration and deceleration around each sample point. Here, the period of the triggering pulse signal must match the rotational speed of the antenna rotator. For example, if a 1 pulse per second (1PPS) trigger signal is used and expects to sample directional CIRs every 10 degrees, the rotational speed should be set as $10^\circ/\text{s}$. As illustrated in Fig. 2,

Fig. 1. The schematic diagram of the proposed correlation-based sub-THz channel sounder using COTS instruments.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the measurement setup when the channel sounder operates in the continuous rotation mode.

Fig. 3. The user interface of the automation control software for the proposed sub-THz channel sounder.

oscilloscope acquiring data only occurs on the rising transition of the trigger edge while crossing a user-specified trigger level. However, the antenna rotator moves at a constant speed only after the acceleration phase, i.e., the Phase #1. Thus, the actual first sampling point lags behind the starting point in order to perform uniform sampling in Phase #2. Here, the continuous rotation mode is adopted for performance validation. Fig. 3 shows the user interface of the customer-design control software using MATLAB[®] App Designer, where all required parameters can be set for initializing the instruments and

TABLE I
SPECIFICATIONS OF THE CHANNEL SOUNDER FOR D-BAND CHANNEL MEASUREMENT

Parameter	Unit	Value
Center frequency	GHz	150
Bandwidth	GHz	2
IF frequency	GHz	6
LO frequency	GHz	24
PA gain	dB	18.5
LNA gain	dB	24.8
Delay resolution	ns	0.5
Sequence length	/	4096
Max. excess delay	μ s	2.05
Tx/Rx ant. gain	dBi	25
Tx/Rx HPBW (Az.)	deg	10
Tx/Rx HPBW (El.)	deg	9
Tx scan range (Az.)	deg	[−60 : 10 : 60]
Tx scan range (El.)	deg	[95 : 9 : 104]
Rx scan range (Az.)	deg	[0 : 10 : 350]
Rx scan range (El.)	deg	[80 : 5 : 95]

running the measurement.

III. INITIAL EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND VALIDATIONS

A. D-Band Channel Measurement Campaign

The D-band double-directional channel measurement campaign is conducted using the sub-THz channel sounder depicted in Fig. 1, which transmits a 4096-length sounding sequence with the bandwidth of 2 GHz at the center frequency of 140 GHz. Identical VDI WR-6.5SAX (110–170 GHz) modules are used, which work in block up- and down-conversion modes at the Tx and Rx sides, respectively. Moreover, they both operate in the high-frequency LO input mode, where the LO signal at a frequency of 24 GHz gets multiplied by a factor of $N = 6$ to 144 GHz and mixes it with the input IF signal at 6 GHz. The LO output power of 5.5 dBm is set to compensate for the cable loss and ensure that the VDI SAX modules operate within the recommended input power specification providing the optimal performance. The specifications of the channel sounder for indoor D-band channel measurement are detailed in Table I.

Fig. 4a shows the indoor corridor measurement environment for performance validations of the proposed sub-THz channel

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. (a) D-band channel measurement environment in the corridor. (b) Perspective view of the simplified ray-tracing model of the concerned environment, as well as the simulation results.

sounder. The Tx is located in the corner of the corridor, where the Tx antenna is fixed at a height of 1.82 m. Two Rx locations are selected, where Rx1 and Rx2 are located in line-of-sight (LOS) and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) scenarios, respectively. The height of the Rx antenna is 0.95 m. The DSS method is performed at both Tx and Rx sides using the identical WR-6 25 dBi standard gain horn antennas from Pasternack with the azimuth and elevation half-power beamwidth (HPBW) of 10° and 9° , respectively. The corresponding antenna scanning ranges are also listed in Table I. Fig. 4b shows the corresponding environment model used for ray-tracing simulation.

B. Calibration and Performance Analysis

Back-to-back measurement was performed via directly connecting Tx and Rx RF front-ends with a 3-inch WR-6 straight waveguide section and a variable attenuator. As shown in Fig. 5, only PA is included in the back-to-back link, while the low noise amplifier (LNA) is excluded due to high-power signal input. The red line represents the system impulse response with an attenuation of 28 dB. In addition, OTA reference measurement is conducted with the Tx-Rx separation distance of 0.3 m. The black dotted line in Fig. 5 represents the power delay profile (PDP) of the OTA link with the same configuration of back-to-back measurement. The delay

Fig. 5. The PDPs of the back-to-back and 30-cm OTA measurements.

difference $\Delta\tau$ between the PDP peaks of the back-to-back and OTA reference measurements is 1 ns, corresponding to an approximate propagation distance of 0.3 m.

C. Validation and Comparison

For each Tx-Rx pair, the number of 3744 ($= 2 \times 13 \times 4 \times 36$) directional CIR $h(\tau, \Omega^{\text{Tx}}, \Omega^{\text{Rx}})$ recorded depends on the number of elevation angle of departure (EOD) θ^{Tx} , azimuth angle of departure (AOD) ϕ^{Tx} , elevation angle of arrival (EOA) θ^{Rx} , and azimuth angle of arrival (AOA) ϕ^{Rx} , respectively, where $\Omega^{\text{Tx}} = (\theta^{\text{Tx}}, \phi^{\text{Tx}})$ and $\Omega^{\text{Rx}} = (\theta^{\text{Rx}}, \phi^{\text{Rx}})$. The directional PDP is calculated with noise thresholding as

$$\hat{P}(\tau, \Omega^{\text{Tx}}, \Omega^{\text{Rx}}) = \begin{cases} |h(\tau, \Omega^{\text{Tx}}, \Omega^{\text{Rx}})|^2, & \text{if } |h|^2 > 4\sigma_{\text{noise}}^2; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where the noise floor σ_{noise}^2 is computed by the variance of the last hundreds of nanoseconds of each directional CIR. Here we adopt about 6 dB power threshold above the noise floor to determine effective PDP.

The power angular spectrum (PAS) characterizes the received power distribution in the angular domain. The double-directional PAS is calculated as the sum of the power on each delay bin in the directional PDP:

$$P(\Omega^{\text{Tx}}, \Omega^{\text{Rx}}) = \sum_i \hat{P}(\tau_i, \Omega^{\text{Tx}}, \Omega^{\text{Rx}}) \quad (2)$$

where $\{\tau_i = \tau \mid |h(\tau, \Omega^{\text{Tx}}, \Omega^{\text{Rx}})|^2 > 4\sigma_{\text{noise}}^2\}$. Moreover, the single-directional PAS with respect to ϕ^{Rx} is calculated as

$$P(\phi^{\text{Rx}}) = \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k \hat{P}(\tau_i, \Omega_j^{\text{Tx}}, \theta_k^{\text{Rx}}, \phi^{\text{Rx}}) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 6 shows the measurement results of the single- and double-directional PASs for two Rx locations. For the LOS receiver (i.e., Rx1), a total of six dominant propagation paths can be detected, including one LOS path and five reflection paths from the surrounding walls. As for the NLOS receiver (i.e., Rx2), four reflection paths can be detected. All detected paths fit well with the ray-tracing simulation results as shown in Fig. 4b. By combining the measurement data with the

Fig. 6. The layout of Tx and Rx locations in corridor environment, as well as the PASs at LOS location (right) and NLOS location (left). Note that the same upper and lower case letters are used for labeling the corresponding paths from ray-tracing simulation (see Fig. 4b).

geometry of the environment, apart from the LOS path, the first-order and even second-order reflection paths from walls can be observed in 150 GHz indoor channels.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a modular correlation-based channel sounder has been developed using the COTS equipment for 6G sub-THz channel measurements. Different from the existing VNA-based solution, the proposed sounder could be easily upgraded to support long-range and time-varying channel measurements across multiple frequency bands. The DSS method operating in the continuous rotation mode significantly reduces the measurement duration of each Tx-Rx location pair, enabling high-efficient collection of a large amount of directional channel data. Initial double-directional D-band channel measurement campaign was conducted in corridor environment. The measurement duration for each Tx-Rx location pair decreases by three times as much as the VNA-based measurement using the same antenna rotation setup. Compared with the ray-tracing simulation results in the identical environment, the identified multipath components show a good agreement with measured PASs in both LOS and NLOS scenarios. We will coordinate larger channel measurement activities in the future for sub-THz radio channel characterization and statistical modeling.

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